

MANAGERIAL COMPETENCE AND FUNCTIONAL MANAGEMENT SKILLS: ITS IMPACT ON TEACHER'S PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

The key purpose of this study is to determine how management and functional management skills of school heads affect the teacher's performance in Lakeside District, Division of San Pablo City during the school year 2019-2020. The specific aims of this research were to seek answers to the following questions: How do the respondents perceive the managerial competence of the school head in terms of: intrapersonal; interpersonal, technical; and leadership? What is the respondent's perception of the school head functional management skills in terms of: planning; organizing; and controlling? What is the level of performance of the respondents during the school year 2019-2020? Is there a significant relationship between the perceived managerial competences to the teachers' performance? Is there a significant relationship between the perceived functional management skills to the teachers' performance? The study employs the descriptive-correlational type of research as it primarily aims to describe the managerial competence and functional management skills of school heads and to determine the relationship of its variables. The simple descriptive statistics such as frequency, distribution, percent, count, mean and standard deviation will be used to quantify and analyze the perception of variables. Pearson r will be applied to find the significant relationship between the managerial competence and functional management skills of school heads and its impact on teachers' performance. Teachers' perceptions of school heads' managerial competence, such as intrapersonal ($r = -.138$), interpersonal ($r = -.134$), technical ($r = -.061$), and leadership ($r = -.069$), as well as teachers' perceptions of functional management skills, such as planning ($r = -.046$), organizing ($r = .001$), and controlling ($r = -.084$), have no significant relationship to IPCRF or performance of teachers, according to the analyzed data. Based on the findings of the study, the following are concluded: The hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between managerial competence and functional management skills of school heads and teacher's performance is partially accepted.

Keywords: Managerial Competence, Functional Management Skill, Teachers' Performance, Philippines